

The Ongoing Ebola Virus Disease Outbreaks in The Democratic Republic Of The Congo: A Real Threat to Global Public Health.

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ABSTRACT

OBJECTIVES:

To highlight the ongoing Ebola Virus Disease outbreaks in the Democratic Republic of the Congo as a real threat to global public health due to a lack of effective vaccines, treatment, and as a bioterrorism agent.

Many challenges to managing these outbreaks include poor health system infrastructures, general insecurity, ongoing war, violence, community resistance, poverty, the current COVID pandemic, and distrust of public health authorities.

METHODS:

A focused literature search was done to find good publications, articles, and news reports that addressed a specific topic related to the Ebola virus disease in the Congo, Sub-Saharan Africa, and lessons learned from the EVD outbreaks and biosecurity and biodefense. On October 28, 2022, articles were discovered using Google Scholar ,PubMed and google search engine.

Currently, there is no effective treatment or vaccine to eradicate EVD. These outbreaks pose a potential risk for biosecurity and bioterrorism, making vaccine development a priority for many nations worldwide.

CONCLUSION:

These findings create opportunities for future prevention and control, such as integrating a community-based, one-health approach, investing in biosecurity and biodefense research, and developing novel diagnostic tools, drugs, and safe vaccines. Lastly, public health intervention for consolidated policy guidelines.

RESULTS:

Based on the articles found, we identified some key facts regarding EVD outbreaks in DR Congo and their consequences on the rest of the world. There have been many Ebola virus disease outbreaks since its discovery in DRC or ex-Zaire back in 1976, and so far, 14 outbreaks have been identified, causing a very high case-fatality rate ranging from 25% to 90%.

Keywords: Ebola virus, EVD in DR Congo, EVD-Bioterrorism, Ebola virus threat to global public health

INTRODUCTION

Ebola, well-known as Ebola hemorrhagic fever, is a deadly zoonotic disease that affects humans and primates. Ebola virus disease (EVD) results from a virus belonging to the filoviridae family and the genus Ebolavirus. This disease has posed diagnostic challenges and has been a universal public health threat since its discovery.⁽¹⁾ The disease was first discovered in Zaire (now the Democratic Republic of Congo) by Dr. Peter Piot in 1976 while investigating a case of alleged yellow fever. The name "Ebola" was given since the disease was found near the Ebola River.⁽²⁾

The natural hosts of Ebola are fruit bats of the Pteropodidae family, such as *Hypsignathus monstrosus*, *Epomops franqueti*, and *Myonycteris torquata*. The infection may be developed by eating fruit bats, and transmission can quickly happen between nonhuman primates and humans. Ebola virus disease has a case fatality ratio of 25–90%.⁽³⁾ The Zaire strain is the most fatal, with an overall higher case-fatality ratio than other strains.⁽³⁾ Ebola virus disease is transmitted primarily through contact with the body fluids of symptomatic patients, most commonly in adults aged 17–44 years, with relative sparing of children younger than 16 years.

Since 1976, DRC has faced 14 outbreaks (Table 2). The most recent was from April to August 2022.⁽⁴⁾ There is no effective vaccine or curative treatment against this deadly disease. Ongoing outbreaks indicate that the DRC government has been struggling to contain EVD. The detection of EVD in one city can readily spread to other parts of the world. On many occasions, these outbreaks have been declared Public Health Emergency of International Concern (PHEIC) for the world to take notice of and redouble its efforts.⁽²⁾

The need for the quick creation of a vaccine is highlighted by the rise in the frequency of EVD outbreaks and the perceived risk that it could be used as a bioterrorism weapon. The World Health

Organization (WHO) created an ethical framework, the Monitored Emergency Use of Unregistered and Investigational Interventions (MEURI), to set the criteria that must be met for consenting patients to access investigational therapeutics outside of clinical trials because Ebola Virus Disease is a threat to the entire world and considering the lack of curative drugs against it.⁽⁵⁾

This paper highlights the significant causes of ongoing EVD in DRC. To better approach this broad topic, the impact of the Ebola Virus Disease on local and global public health will be reviewed. Moreover, commonly interpreted challenges will be reviewed as well.

METHODS

A focused literature search was conducted to find published articles, news reports, or educational websites from reliable sources to support this commentary-style paper. After a brief discussion on the topic with the Teaching Fellow, four criteria were used to determine the information sources: ⁽¹⁾ they had to be in the English language; ⁽²⁾ they had to be related to the Ebola virus Disease in the Congo; ⁽³⁾ they had to report data about Ebola virus disease; ⁽⁴⁾ they had to inform the threat of EVD on global public health and ⁽⁴⁾ they had to come from experts in the field of public health. The search was done using Google Scholar, PubMed, and google search engine to identify reliable websites. Publications containing the keywords of interest were included. The initial search started on October 28, 2022, and was completed on October 31, 2022.

Table 1: Summary of sources and information analyzed

EVD in the Congo		
<i>Publication title and author</i>	<i>Publication type/source</i>	<i>Type of information</i>
<p>The ongoing Ebola epidemic in the Democratic Republic of Congo, 2018–2019.</p> <p>Ilunga Kalenga, O., Moeti, M., Sparrow, A., Nguyen, V. K., Lucey, D., & Ghebreyesus, T. A.</p>	<p><i>Journal article</i></p> <p><u><i>New England Journal of Medicine</i></u></p> <p>2019</p>	<p>Expert inferences and comments of current knowledge and direct observations</p>
<p>Forty-two years of responding to Ebola virus outbreaks in Sub-Saharan Africa: a review</p> <p>Rugarabamu, S., Mboera, L., Rweyemamu, M., Mwanyika, G., Lutwama, J., Paweska, J., & Misinzo, G.</p>	<p><i>Journal article</i></p> <p><u><i>BMJ Global Health</i></u></p> <p>2020</p>	<p>Expert inferences and comments of current knowledge and direct observations</p>
<p>Ethics of emerging infectious disease outbreak responses: Using Ebola virus disease as a case study of limited resource allocation.</p> <p>Nichol, A. A., & Antierens, A.</p>	<p><i>Journal article</i></p> <p><u><i>PloS one</i></u></p> <p>2021</p>	<p>Expert inferences and comments of current knowledge and direct observations</p>
<p>History of Ebola Virus Disease (EVD) Outbreaks</p> <p>CDC</p>	<p>Web article</p> <p><u><i>CDC</i></u></p> <p>2022</p>	<p>CDC citing current data and information regarding infection observations</p>
<p>The exacerbation of Ebola outbreaks by conflict in the Democratic Republic of the Congo.</p> <p>Wells, C. R., Pandey, A., Ndeffo Mbah, M. L., Gaüzère, B. A., Malvy, D., Singer, B. H.,</p>	<p><i>Journal article</i></p> <p><u><i>Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences</i></u></p> <p>2019</p>	<p>Expert inferences and comments of current knowledge and direct observations</p>

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& Galvani, A. P.		
Recurrent Ebolavirus disease in the Democratic Republic of Congo: update and challenges. Inungu, J., Iheduru-Anderson, K., & Odio, O. J.	<i>Journal article</i> <u>AIMS public health</u> 2019	Expert inferences and comments of current knowledge and direct observations
World Health Organization. (1978). Ebola haemorrhagic fever in Zaire, 1976.	Disease report <u>Report of an international commission.</u> 1978	Report from WHO

Dual COVID-19 and Ebola epidemics

<i>Publication title and author</i>	<i>Publication type/source</i>	<i>Type of information</i>
Ebola and COVID-19 in Democratic Republic of Congo: grappling with two plagues at once. Khan, F. M. A., Hasan, M. M., Ahmad, S., & Essar, M. Y	<i>Journal article</i> <u>Tropical Medicine and Health</u> 2021	Expert inferences and comments of current knowledge and direct observations
"Responding to the challenge of the dual COVID-19 and Ebola epidemics in the Democratic Republic of Congo—priorities for achieving control Nachega, J. B., Mbala-Kingebeni, P., Otshudiema, J., Mobula, L. M., Preiser, W., Kallay, O., ... & Tam-Fum, J. J. M	<i>Journal article</i> <u>The American journal of tropical medicine and hygiene</u> 2020	Expert inferences and comments of current knowledge and direct observations

Ebola Virus: Global Public Health threat

<i>Publication title and author</i>	<i>Publication type/source</i>	<i>Type of information</i>
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Emergent threats: lessons learnt from Ebola Piot, Peter, Moses J. Soka, and Julia Spencer	<i>Journal article</i> <u><i>International health</i></u> 2019	Expert inferences and comments of current knowledge and direct observations
Ebola viral disease in West Africa: a threat to global health, economy and political stability Omoleke, Semeeh Akinwale, Ibrahim Mohammed, and Yauba Saidu.	<i>Journal article</i> <u><i>Journal of public health in Africa</i></u> 2016	Expert inferences and comments of current knowledge and direct observations
Biosecurity and Biodefense: Lessons from Ebola Virus Outbreak. Lebea, Phiyani J.	Editorial scholar.archive.org <u>2014</u>	Expert insight and comments on current knowledge and observations
"Ebola virus: A global public health menace: A narrative review. Hasan, S., Ahmad, S. A., Masood, R., & Saeed, S	Journal article <u><i>Journal of family medicine and primary care</i></u> 2019	Expert insight and comments on current knowledge and observations

PHYSIOPATHOLOGY, EPIDEMIOLOGY, CLINICAL PRESENTATION, VACCINE

<i>Publication title and author</i>	<i>Publication type/source</i>	<i>Type of information</i>
Use of Ebola Vaccine: Recommendations of the Advisory Committee on Immunization Practices Choi, M. J., Cossaboom, C. M., Whitesell, A. N., Dyal, J. W., Joyce, A., Morgan, R. L., ... & Frey, S. E.	Disease report <u><i>Morbidity and Mortality Weekly Report (US Dept. of Health and Human Services/CDC)</i></u> 2021	MMWR from the CDC citing current data and information regarding infection observations

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<p>The pathogenesis of Ebola virus disease.</p> <p>Baseler, L., Chertow, D. S., Johnson, K. M., Feldmann, H., & Morens, D. M</p>	<p>Disease report</p> <p><i>Annu Rev Pathol</i></p> <p>2017</p>	<p>Report citing current data and information regarding infection observations</p>
<p>"Understanding ebola virus transmission."</p> <p>Judson, Seth, Joseph Prescott, and Vincent Munster.</p>	<p><i>Journal article</i></p> <p><i>Viruses</i></p> <p>2015</p>	<p>Expert inferences and comments of current knowledge and direct observations</p>

RESULTS

EVD IN THE CONGO

The Congo has faced so many EVD outbreaks since discovering the virus near the Ebola River in 1976. These ongoing EVD outbreaks have case-fatality rates ranging from 25% to 90%. EVD epidemics have been reported in regions with protracted violence, a proliferation of armed groups, and extensive population movement across porous international borders with South Sudan, Uganda, and Rwanda. Political tensions related to contentious national elections add to the various operational constraints that persistent insecurity brings on. Violence against EVD response workers and facilities has increased, which has worsened the virus's transmission. ⁽⁶⁾

Since its discovery, the virus has emerged periodically and infected many people in different African countries and worldwide.

Other types of Ebola virus have been identified in different parts of the world, but the Zaire Ebola virus is deadly, with higher case-fatality rates.

The most recent outbreak, which had a 100% case-fatality rate, lasted from April through August 2022. The first confirmed case in this outbreak's sequencing data revealed that this was a brand-new spillover event from an animal to a person and was not closely related to earlier outbreaks. The following four cases, reported from the Mbandaka and Wangata health zones, were epidemiologically related or had previous contact with an EVD patient. On July 4, 2022, the pandemic was deemed to be over. ⁽⁴⁾

The DRC government's reaction to the most recent outbreaks was implementing a package of treatments, including case detection and fast isolation, contact tracing, population mapping, and identifying high-risk locations to guide a coordinated effort. The integrated effort involved screening, ring vaccination, and GeneXpert (Cepheid) polymerase chain reaction laboratory diagnostics. ⁽²⁾⁽³⁾

REGN-EB3 and mAb114 have shown promise in the last couple of years as treatments against EVD.

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Additionally, one investigational vaccine (rVSV-ZEBOV-GP) was tried first, followed by a second prophylactic vaccine (Ad26.ZEBOV/MVA-BN-Filo) to reinforce the prevention. Although the mainstay of managing EVD outbreaks continues to be the provision of supportive clinical care, the DRC response to these outbreaks has faced many challenges, including continuous war, general insecurity, violence and community resistance, appalling poverty, and a distrust of public health authorities. Ebolavirus remains a real threat to global public health. A fully curative treatment and vaccine are doubtful to be a game-changer given the settings of transmission, zoonotic nature, limits of the effectiveness of any therapeutic intervention, length of these outbreaks, and timing of presentation. ⁽²⁾

In the past four decades, more than 34 outbreaks affected 11 countries in Sub-Saharan Africa. Almost half of these outbreaks were attributed to the Democratic Republic of the Congo. The overall case fatality rate (95% CI) was 66% (62 to 71) and did not change

substantially over time (OR in 2019 vs. 1976=1.6 (95% CI 1.5 to 1.8), $p < 0.001$). The results of this review indicate that there are many challenges to controlling these outbreaks in DR Congo, and most of these challenges are related to epidemiological, sociocultural, and health system factors. ⁽⁷⁾

The Eastern part of DR Congo has been experiencing an elevated frequency of conflict due to mineral resources. This period of civil unrest has negatively impacted the detection and delayed reporting of most outbreaks.

During the conflict, case isolation and ring vaccination were severely obstructed, so only 20% of contacts could be traced. ⁽⁸⁾

In 2018 there was much trouble caused by the presidential election's postponement, which led to hostility towards the public health response teams because of their association with the government. For instance, residents refused to cooperate, which weakened cooperation and sparked conflict by associating the Médecins Sans Frontières (MSF) teams with the DRC Ministry of Health. ⁽²⁾

Dual COVID-19 and Ebola epidemics in DRC

The COVID-19 pandemic harmed the epidemiological control of many infectious diseases. Reports predicted a concomitant increase in Ebola cases during COVID-19 in DRC even before the 2021 outbreak, as many Ebola community outreach initiatives were discontinued. ⁽²⁾ Strict lockdowns jeopardized Ebola control efforts, resulting in ineffective contact tracing and surveillance. As a result, multiple Ebola response workforces were diverted to managing the COVID-19 pandemic. Additionally, the national leadership of the Ebola response was deemed responsible for overseeing DRC's COVID-19 response. This loss in workforce, measures, and attention seriously jeopardized the continuation of effective EVD surveillance. ⁽⁹⁾

Although COVID-19 has created enormous challenges that jeopardized DRC's health, wealth, and social structure, several lessons have been learned from controlling the previous cataclysmic Ebola virus eruptions that were vital in launching the current COVID-19 health countermeasures. These include working with community leaders and groups to fight EVD and provide crucial information to the general public in native languages. The COVID-19 response has received the foundations and workforces of the Ebola virus. ⁽⁹⁾

According to the WHO, as of June 9, 2020, a total of twelve EVD cases (nine confirmed and three probable), including nine deaths (case fatality rate 75%), were reported in three affected health zones (Wangata, Mbandaka, and Bikoro). 85.3% (521/611) of contacts were traced, but none were suspected EVD cases. Also, 1,495 people, including 436 frontline health professionals and close contacts, have been vaccinated using the rVSV-ZEBOV-GP vaccine since the beginning of this outbreak. ⁽¹⁰⁾

Global Public Health threat

With deepening globalization, these ongoing EVD outbreaks are increasingly mobile, and their threats are global. ⁽¹¹⁾

The EVD outbreaks pose a biosecurity⁽¹⁶⁾ danger identified about 46 years ago. This is a genuine global health issue. The threat is urgent in the Congo, where

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the health system lacks the essential capabilities to contain these outbreaks. Most nations worldwide lack disease surveillance systems to track and quarantine contacts and isolation and treatment facilities to care for patients. A single epidemic has posed significant bio-security dangers to the affected countries and the international community. ⁽¹²⁾

Since it is well known that the outbreaks pose a threat to our health security, the Ebola virus could easily cross international borders. Infected individuals have traveled across borders within Africa, Europe, and North America, where they unintentionally started small chains of transmission far from the outbreak's epicenter. ⁽²⁾

The urgency of developing an effective vaccine and drug is highlighted by the rising frequency of these EVD outbreaks and the apparent risk that it could be used as a bioterrorism agent ⁽²⁾. The World Health Organization (WHO) created an ethical framework, the Monitored Emergency Use of Unregistered and Investigational Interventions (MEURI) ⁽²⁾, to establish the requirements that should be met for consenting patients to access investigational therapeutics outside of clinical trials because EVD is a threat to the entire world and due to lack of effective treatments against it. Patients with laboratory-confirmed EBOVD in the DRC were treated with three antibody-based therapeutics (mAb114, ZMapp, and REGN-EB3) and one antiviral medication (Remdesivir) as part of MEURI's groundbreaking exploratory interventions that were accelerated. ⁽²⁾

DISCUSSION

For almost 46 years, EVD has repeatedly been reemerging in the Democratic Republic of Congo, causing widespread hemorrhagic fever outbreaks with case fatality ranging from 25-90%, sometimes 100%. So far, DRC has had the highest number of outbreaks compared to any other county worldwide. (table 2)

These continuous outbreaks could quickly spread to other countries and become a pandemic. The Ebola virus could be used as a bioterrorism agent, making the development of effective vaccines and drugs a high priority for many countries.

The Ebola virus is a filamentous, enveloped, negative-sense RNA genome of approximately 19 kb. It belongs to the Filoviridae family, causing severe hemorrhagic fever in humans and nonhuman primates.

The filoviridae family has three genera: Cuevavirus, Marburgvirus, and Ebolavirus. Among Ebolavirus (figure 1) ⁽¹⁴⁾ species, five species have been identified: Sudan Ebolavirus (SEBOV); Zaire Ebolavirus (ZEBOV); Côte d'Ivoire Ebolavirus (aka Ivory Coast Ebolavirus (ICEBOV)); Reston Ebolavirus (REBOV) and Bundibugyo Ebolavirus (BEBOV). ZEBOV is the most commonly found in DR Congo and is very deadly.

Although the precise mechanism of transmission remains questionable, fruit bats, chimpanzees, gorillas, monkeys, forest antelopes, and porcupines are thought to be possible natural hosts. ⁽²⁾

Potential routes of EBOV transmission have been identified. Small, virus-filled droplets inhaled into the air or inhaled into an aerosol can spread a virus when they evaporate before touching a surface and leave behind infectious droplet nuclei that can travel long distances. Aerosols are commonly used to refer to the tiny droplets that can produce these droplet nuclei. However, they can also be used to describe any small liquid or solid particles that are floating in the atmosphere. Currently, there is no data explaining whether EBOV forms droplet nuclei.

The term "droplet transmission," also known as "big droplet transmission," describes coming into touch with infectious droplets that do not dissipate or travel far. Although these droplets move through the air, they are not the same as aerosols, which evaporate to produce droplet nuclei.

Any surface a pathogen may survive on is referred to as a fomite, and fomite transmission can happen when a person touches that infected surface. Touching items that have been in contact with Ebola patients or other surfaces contaminated with EBOV-containing human fluids are examples of potential EBOV fomite transmission pathways. Direct bodily contact with bodily fluids is the most likely way for people to contract EBOV of all the possible transmission mechanisms. Epidemiological information, tests with

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NHPs, and circumstantial evidence from prior epidemics all show that contact with EBOV-infected fluids through mucosal membranes, injections, or open wounds might cause infection. ⁽¹³⁾

Within 2 to 21 days of the virus encounter, symptoms can start to show up, with an average onset time of 8 to 10 days. Usually, when a person gets sicker, the sickness moves from "dry" symptoms at first (such as fever, aches, and weariness) to "wet" symptoms (such as vomiting and diarrhea).

EVD symptoms and signs may include fever, weakness and fatigue, loss of appetite, sore throat, unexplained hemorrhaging, bleeding or bruising, and gastrointestinal symptoms, including abdominal pain, diarrhea, and vomiting. Other symptoms may include skin rash, red eyes, and hiccups (late-stage).

EVD can be diagnosed by antibody-capture enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay (ELISA), antigen-capture detection tests, serum neutralization test, reverse transcriptase polymerase chain reaction (RT-PCR) assay, and sequencing and genetic analysis.

Prevention may involve:

- Avoid getting in contact with infected people's blood and bodily fluids, including their urine, sweat, feces, saliva, vomit, breast milk, amniotic fluid, semen, and vaginal secretion

- Avoid touching anything that may have come into contact with a sick person's blood or other bodily fluids (such as clothes, bedding, needles, and medical equipment).

- Avoid touching the body of a person who died from EVD during funeral or burial rituals.

- Avoid coming into contact with bats, woodland antelopes, nonhuman primates (such as monkeys and chimpanzees), and raw meat from these or other animals (bushmeat).

On December 19, 2019, the American Food and Drug Administration (FDA) authorized the rVSV-ZEBOV Ebola vaccine, also known as Ervebo®. This is the first Ebola vaccine that the FDA has approved.

This single-dose vaccine is safe and protective against the Zaire ebolavirus, which has caused the most significant and deadly Ebola outbreaks to date. ⁽⁴⁾

For persons over 18 in the US population who may be at risk of occupational exposure to the Zaire ebolavirus, the Advisory Committee on Immunization Practices (ACIP) advised pre-exposure prophylactic immunization with rVSV-ZEBOV on February 26, 2020. ⁽¹⁵⁾

Two treatments against Zaire ebola virus showed some promise. FDA approved Inmazeb, a combination of three monoclonal antibodies, in October 2020, and Ebanga, a single monoclonal antibody, was approved in December 2020. ⁽¹⁵⁾

More data are still needed to evaluate the effectiveness of these drugs and vaccines.

When given early, basic interventions can dramatically increase the odds of survival whether or not other treatments are available.

These measures are categorized as supportive care:

- Supplying fluids and electrolytes (body salts) orally or intravenously (intravenously).

- Taking medication to stabilize blood pressure, decrease nausea and vomiting, control fever, and ease the pain.

The CDC released national capability criteria in 2011 to direct the development of local, state, and federal public health disaster preparation initiatives. Planning for and responding to the Ebola virus needs readiness in six essential public health preparedness areas and one hospital area, including:

- Healthcare System Preparedness: Develop local and state emergency operations plans that address the concerns and particular needs of healthcare facilities for the Ebola response while considering the need for adequate care and infection control of identified patients and persons under investigation.

- Emergency Public Information and Warning: Prepare messages on risk communication for internal personnel

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and the general public, including general information about Ebola, dangers to the public, risk of transmission, and preventative measures.

- Information Sharing: Ascertain that the proper personnel are enrolled in information systems and are receiving CDC Health Alert Network (HAN) notifications.

- Non-Pharmaceutical Interventions: Review the CDC's Interim Guidance for Monitoring and Movement of Persons with Ebola virus Exposure and make sure state and local epidemiologic and medical professionals are up to date on travel advice.

- Public Health Laboratory Testing: Make sure that clinical laboratories review lab safety standards and practices, including the proper use of PPE, and that

they have the right amount of PPE.

- Public Health Surveillance and Epidemiological Investigation: Establish an execution plan and ensure state and local epidemiologic staff have access to epidemiological tools.

- Responder Safety and Health: Ensure PPE is adequately stocked at the state and municipal levels and that responders and medical professionals have received training on its proper application. Likewise, ensure clinicians and first responders have read the CDC's advice on worker safety.⁽⁴⁾

CONCLUSION

The Congo is still experiencing repetitive EVD outbreaks posing a considerable threat to local and global public health. Effective vaccines and drugs are the cornerstones to stopping these ongoing Ebola virus outbreaks. One-health approach is likely to provide an excellent understanding to prevent and control the disease at source.

More research must be done to develop vaccines to protect human communities and the fauna they interact with. Improving the healthcare system and medical infrastructures, investing in biosecurity, and

biodefense research should be prioritized to prevent future Ebola virus disease outbreaks and pandemics.

Community engagement and participation are essential factors in the appropriate containment of an outbreak and in preventing its further transmission.

Finally, the Congo should adopt and implement consolidated policy guidelines to stop these outbreaks.

TABLES AND FIGURES

Table 2: Chronology of EVD outbreaks in DRC- CDC data

Year of Outbreak	Species	Reported number of cases	Reported number of deaths and percentage of fatal cases	Province
2022	Zaire Ebolavirus	5	5(100%)	Équateur
2021	Zaire Ebolavirus	11	6(55%)	Nord Kivu
2021	Zaire Ebolavirus	12	6(50%)	Nord Kivu
2020	Zaire Ebolavirus	130	55 (42.3%)	Équateur
2018-2020	Zaire Ebolavirus	3470	2287 (66%)	North Kivu
2018	Zaire Ebolavirus	54	33 (61%)	Équateur
2017	Zaire Ebolavirus	8	4 (50%)	Bas UELE
2014	Zaire Ebolavirus	65	49 (71%)	Équateur
2012	Bundibugyo	36	13 (36%)	Orientale
2008/2009	Zaire Ebolavirus	32	15 (47%)	Kasai
2007	Zaire Ebolavirus	264	187 (71%)	Kasai
1995	Zaire Ebolavirus	315	250 (79%)	Bandundu
1977	Zaire Ebolavirus	1	1 (100%)	Orientale
1976	Zaire Ebolavirus	317	280 (88%)	Équateur

Figure 1: Ebola virus structure .⁽¹⁴⁾

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